

Exploring Adapted Yoga as an Empowering Tool for Children with Disabilities

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Abstract:

This paper explores the utilization of adapted yoga as an empowering tool for children with disabilities. By tailoring traditional yoga practices to accommodate the diverse needs of this demographic, the study investigates its potential in fostering holistic development and enhancing their quality of life. Through a combination of literature review and practical insights, the research elucidates the physical, emotional, and social benefits of adapted yoga interventions. It also addresses the challenges and considerations inherent in implementing such programs in educational and therapeutic settings. Overall, this paper contributes to the understanding of adapted yoga as a promising opportunity for empowering children with disabilities.

Keywords: adapted yoga, children, disabilities, empowerment, holistic development

Introduction:

Yoga has its origin thousands of years ago in India. It has originated from a universal desire to attaining happiness and getting rid of sufferings. According to yogic lore, Shiva is considered the founder of yoga. A number of seals and fossil remains of Indus Valley Civilisation, dating back to 2700 BC indicates that yoga was prevalent in ancient India. However, systematic reference of yoga is found in Patanjali's Yogadarshana. Maharishi Patanjali systematised the yogic practices. After Patanjali, many sages/yogis contributed to its development and as a result yoga has now spread all over the world. Yoga is a spiritual practice that aims to balance and harmonize the body, mind, and emotions through various techniques such as asanas, pranayama, mudra, bandha, shatkarma, and meditation. The ultimate goal of yoga is the union of individual

consciousness with universal consciousness. Yoga has been practiced in India for centuries and there are various schools of thought within the practice.

Regular practice of yoga has been shown to improve microcirculation, leading to better oxygen supply to all organs and tissues of the body, which can slow down the aging process and improve stress competence. With increasing overcrowding, stress, pollution, and the fast pace of life, there is a growing need for lifestyle changes that can reduce the negative impact on health and happiness. Yoga is one such option that has been recommended for reducing these negative effects. Studies conducted worldwide have shown that regular and correct practice of yoga can promote health and prevent certain diseases. In the past, many people were not aware of what yoga is, and some believed it to be akin to a "magical performance" such as bending bars and stopping the pulse. Children with disabilities often encounter barriers to participating in physical activities that promote well-being and empowerment. Traditional forms of exercise and therapy may not fully accommodate their diverse needs. However, adapted yoga has emerged as a promising avenue for addressing these challenges, offering tailored practices that encompass modified poses, breathing exercises, and relaxation techniques. Among the various adapted yoga poses, Padmasana (Lotus Pose) stand out as foundational postures with potential benefits for physical strength, balance, and mental focus. This study aims to explore the effectiveness of adapted yoga, focusing separately on Padmasana as an empowering tool for children with disabilities. However, in recent times, there is an increasing interest in knowing what specific yoga practices can be followed for maintaining health or overcoming common health problems.

Children with disabilities face complex challenges due to a combination of physical, cognitive, sensory, and/or behavioural impairments. They require individualized support to address their unique needs and abilities. Despite their challenges, these children demonstrate resilience and possess unique strengths. Inclusive environments and tailored interventions are essential for promoting their well-being and participation. Adapted yoga offers a promising approach to support their physical, emotional, and social development.

Objectives:

For Padmasana (Lotus Pose):

- To assess the impact of adapted yoga sessions incorporating Padmasana on the physical and emotional well-being of children with disabilities.
- To explore the potential benefits of Padmasana in improving concentration and relaxation abilities in children with disabilities.

Purpose of the Study:

The purpose of this study is to investigate the effects of Padmasana practice within adapted yoga sessions on the physical and emotional well-being of children with disabilities. By examining the hypotheses through pre and post-tests, this study aims to contribute to the understanding of Padmasana as a potential empowering tool for this population.

Hypotheses:

(H1): Participating in adapted yoga sessions focusing on Padmasana significantly improves physical well-being and emotional wellbeing scores in children with disabilities.

Review of literature:

Neelam R. (2020). explores yoga benefits concentration, flexibility, strength, and stress reduction for individuals with disabilities. Telles, Shah, and Balkrishna's work underscores yoga's positive impact on mobility, digestion, self-regulation, and social adaptation. Collectively, these studies affirm yoga's potential to improve the overall well-being of individuals with disabilities.

The literature supports yoga as a mindfulness intervention for adolescents coping with chronic adversity. Van der Kolk (2020) research underscores the impact of stress, while Beltran et al. advocate for physically-based therapies in underserved areas. This study

evaluates yoga's potential to improve emotion regulation and reduce perceived stress, noting the necessity for larger-scale investigations.

Claire T. Kelly (2019) Literature underscores self-determination and anxiety challenges in individuals with intellectual and developmental disabilities. Autonomy-supportive interventions hold promise for improvement. This study investigates a six-week autonomy-supportive yoga program, employing mixed methods. Preliminary findings indicate positive changes, including heightened self-determination and reduced anxiety.

Methodology:

The participant are taken from the special school 4 participants, Age group: 6 to 14 years, participants from the CP, ID, and ASD. Mild level Children's, Intervention period for 3 months totally 20 session one to one session conducted with the help of class teacher and yoga teacher the intervention given for children with disabilities the pre-test conducted before intervention & post test conducted after the intervention period.

Sl.No	Students name:	Types of disability
1.	Sample 1	CP with associated condition
2.	Sample 2	ID with associated condition
3.	Sample 3	ASD+ associated condition
4.	Sample 4	CP+ID

Padmasana:

Padmasana is made of two words: Padma and asana. Padma means 'lotus'. The legs in the sitting position of this asana give the appearance of a lotus.

This is a meditative asana.

Padmasana by following the steps given below:

Starting position: Sit on the ground.

1. Slowly fold the right leg and place right foot on the left thigh close to the pelvic bone. The right heel should be pressing the lower part of the abdomen.
2. Slowly and carefully fold the left leg and place it on right thigh. The heel should press lower part of abdomen.
3. Form jnana mudra with your hands. For jnana mudra, fold index finger and join the tips of your thumb and index finger. Keep other fingers straight.
4. Keep the hands in jnana mudra on knees. Keep the body straight and maintain the position.

Releasing position:

5. Remove left leg from the thigh and then remove right leg and come to the starting position

Remember the following points:

Do's Don'ts

- Knees should touch the ground in final position.
- Keep head and spine erect and shoulders relaxed.
- Keep the arms relaxed in the final position
- Do not bend forward and backward in the final posture.
- Do not tense the arms.

Benefits

- It is good for concentration and memory.

- It brings calmness and peace.
- It is good for digestion.
- It stretches leg muscles and brings flexibility in legs.

Limitation

- Person suffering from pain or injury in knees or sciatica should not practise this asana.

Scoring Key

5- Individually

4- Gestural prompt

3- Verbal prompt

2- Physical prompt

1- Modelling

Results and Discussion:

(H1): Participating in adapted yoga sessions focusing on Padmasana significantly improves physical well-being and emotional wellbeing scores in children with disabilities.

Table 4: Table showing the result on Participating in adapted yoga sessions focusing on Padmasana

Domain:	N	Mean	S.D	df	't' value	Sig
Pre-test	4	26.00	2.00	3		

					21	.001
Post-test	4	36.50	1.00	3		

Figure 1: Graphical representation of result on Participating in adapted yoga sessions focusing on Padmasana

Interpretation:

The significant increase in mean scores from pre-test (26.00) to post-test (36.50) suggests that participating in adapted yoga sessions focusing on Padmasana has a positive impact on both physical and emotional well-being in children with disabilities. The highly significant p-value (< 0.001) indicates strong evidence supporting the effectiveness of the yoga intervention. Therefore, the results support the hypothesis (H1) that participating in adapted yoga sessions focusing on Padmasana significantly improves physical and emotional well-being scores in children with disabilities.

Findings:

Enhanced Physical and Emotional Well-being: The significant increase in mean scores from the pre-test (26.00) to the post-test (36.50) phase underscores the positive impact of the adapted yoga sessions on both physical and emotional well-being. This suggests that the intervention effectively addresses the holistic needs of children with disabilities, leading to improvements in various aspects of their overall well-being.

Effectiveness of 20-Session Intervention: The prolonged duration of the 20-session intervention likely contributed to the substantial improvements observed in physical and emotional well-being. The extended period allowed for more comprehensive exploration and integration of Padmasana and other yoga practices, facilitating deeper relaxation, improved flexibility, and enhanced emotional regulation among participants.

The findings align closely with the hypothesis (H1) that participating in adapted yoga sessions focusing on Padmasana significantly improves physical and emotional well-being scores in children with disabilities. The empirical evidence from this study provides compelling support for the efficacy of yoga as a beneficial intervention for this population, reinforcing the importance of incorporating yoga into their holistic care plans.

Conclusion:

The results of this study demonstrate that participating in adapted yoga sessions focusing on Padmasana has a significant positive impact on the physical and emotional well-being of children with disabilities. The substantial increase in mean scores from the pre-test to the post-test phase indicates marked improvements in both domains. Additionally, the highly significant p-value (< 0.001) provides robust evidence supporting the effectiveness of the yoga intervention. Therefore, the findings strongly support the hypothesis (H1) that participating in adapted yoga sessions focusing on Padmasana significantly enhances physical and emotional well-being scores in children with disabilities.

Reference:

1. Ramanathan, M. (2020) Yoga for the Differently-Abled Children.
2. Pinellas, M. E. (2020). Fostering Resilience: A Pilot Study for Mindful Yoga as an Intervention for Adolescents Exposed to Chronic Adversity (Doctoral dissertation, National Louis University).

3. Kelly, C. T. (2019). The Impact of an Autonomy-Supportive Yoga Intervention on the Self Determination and Anxiety of Individuals with Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities: A Multi-Method Approach (Doctoral dissertation, Clemson University).
4. Developing an Appropriate Methodology, International Journal of Technology and Inclusive Education (IJTIE).
5. Hawkins BL, Stegall JB, Weber MF, Ryan JB. 2012 The influence of a yoga exercise program for young adults with intellectual disabilities. International Journal yoga.
6. Porter, J. (2012). Yoga as an Effective Behavioural Intervention for Children Diagnosed with an Autism Spectrum Disorder. Graduate Annual, Philadelphia, USA, 1(9), pp. 25-30.